

2025 NASA SMD Open Source Science Data Repositories Workshop

Levels of Service - In-Person
August 25, 2025

- Facilitators: Deborah Smith
- Note-Taker: McKenzie Hicks
- Chat monitor: Cherrelle Tucker

ALL DAY MATERIALS CAN BE FOUND HERE

Agenda

- Visit each of five activity stations in small groups (online visit breakout rooms)
- A bell will ring to signal change to another station - mix up and join a new group
- Levels of Service Model Concept - *Deborah Smith*

Group 1:

- There is a level of service model for earth science - trying to take this model and make it applicable to all SMDs
- Divisions of funding categories can be tweaked across divisions
- None of the current listed items apply to life science data
- How many service levels are required per SMD?
 - Helio: as few as possible
 - Is 3 sufficient? Yes or no? What are the best ways of saying it per SMD?
- PS -Maybe we start with standard/basic and then work up to more in depth levels
- BPS - What level of granularity do we need to look at?
- Don't want to break down derived data into more specific categories
- Worth our effort to make this available and may be dependent on the variants of data
- Need to consider simulations and models that are contributed
- Research artifacts are what we are thinking about here. Shouldn't try to cram them all together but need to make sure to differentiate where appropriate
- PS- we only use one level of service

Group 2:

- There is confusion of different concepts within the LOS models
 - A lot of discussion across the divisions of the different data types to get the right terms

- If you had to divide your data up? What way would you do that? - the answer to this question is helpful to planning the model
- Astro - processing level categorically will not work. Missions operate as solo. There are different definitions for the same terms across missions
- Raw data may mean something different to different people but it is still the most fundamental data
- Reduced data = partially processed - different areas use different terms
- From steward perspective - have to query data providers on what the data meant in order to correctly process it. Need to create a common understanding
- When it comes to layers of service -3 levels is good for PS
- Mission gets a lot more comprehensive

Group 3

- For the categories - data category and then across the top, the level of service and then boxes for which repository the data goes to
 - The impact of the product is more important than the funding
 - Can determine if the project is risky
 - People know where to go to find the data
 - This approach wouldn't work for all the SMDs like it would work for PS (drawing on left hand side)
 - Edit - instead of LOS do data processing level and put LOS with the repositories
- Science mission products don't all get the same level
 - Just have to make it discoverable
- What is the difference between basic and standard?

Group 4:

- Online

Group 5

- Working group that is rewriting the LOS for earth
- Are we archiving non-nasa funded data?
- For bps - have research data in psi that is not our pi but our pis are using them
 - Data is being archived
- Mission support data is a good category to add
- In the comprehensive level of service category - it is still a negotiation
 - Needs to be clear what is optional
- The low medium and high level component is the key part to successfully determining the LOS
- LOS working group - see if this can be revived
- Better communication is what is needed
- Everybody's need can be met with enough categories and breakdowns but not every division may use each category
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Speaker/Lightning Talk Notes

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Webex Chat Comments

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Q&A

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